

IT LANGUAGE AND COMPUTER SCIENCE

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Abstract: In this article, the main purpose of teaching students in the middle school to clarify personal skills of every student, giving them proper education, life enhancing innovative technological world. Principal goal is to teach students to speak fluently in English, writing and reading comprehension skills.

Key words: techniques, technology, principles, method, communication strategies.

INTRODUCTION

I have stated how basic foreign language teaching methods can present the theory of language, their features, and principles. A few imaginative methods of educating might be interactive media, the combination of different computerized media types such as content, pictures, audio and video, into multi-sensory intelligently application or introduction to communicate data to an gathering of people. There are different strategies of teaching. Moreover, we should make them believe their own skills and establish feel happy attitude. I vigorously search and use technologies in my own work. It lets us to work together with learners and give them motivation. As of late, development advances are utilized all the more frequently in optional schools. It's new methods for advancements as well as new structures and strategies for educating, another way to deal with the way toward learning. The fundamental reason for language educating is centered on creating open culture of understudies, instructing in the useful authority of English language. For the advancement of intellectual movement of understudies at English exercises we utilize the accompanying inventive advances. The principle attributes of utilizing present day imaginative advancements is the capacity of separation and individualization of instruction, and furthermore the likelihood of improvement subjective exercises of understudies. The errand of instructors is to make the states of down to earth language learning for every understudy to pick such techniques for preparing which enable each understudy to demonstrate their action, their inventiveness, to make progressively dynamic understudy's psychological exercises in learning English language. The reason of education isn't fair making a understudy proficient, but includes method of reasoning considering, information capacity and self adequacy. That's why educating these days must incorporate inventive communication strategies that confer information. A few imaginative methods of educating might be interactive media, the combination of different computerized media types such as content, pictures, audio and video, into multi-sensory intelligently application or introduction to communicate data to an gathering of people. There are different strategies of teaching. They are: interactive media educating, amusement instructing and so on. But all think or favor something modern and simple. A few individuals favor another strategy of educating. They think that inventive educating is advanced and basic. The utilize of inventive strategies in instructive educate has the potential not only to progress instruction, but too to engage individuals, fortify administration and galvanize the exertion to realize the human improvement objective for the nation. But as for me we need to propose exceptionally basic and exceptionally simple strategy of learning English well. The reason of this paper is to assess the strategies for

educating lexicon as well as mixed media educating and to propose other valuable instructing strategies that can be endeavored in conferring information to the understudies [1;25p].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The significance of training is a motor for the development and advancement of any general public. It confers information, abilities and instills values, but on the other hand is in charge of building human capital which breeds, drives and sets mechanical advancement and financial development. These days' data and information emerge as vital and basic contribution for development and survival. Instead of taking a gander at training just as methods for accomplishing social up, the general public must view instruction additionally as a motor of headway in a data period pushed by its wheels of learning and research prompting advancement. At present, numerous foundations are moving towards issue based learning as an answer for delivering graduates who are inventive and can think basically, scientifically, and take care of issues. Since information is never again an end yet a way to making better issue solvers and empower deep rooted learning. Issue based learning is ending up progressively well known in instructive organizations as an apparatus to address the insufficiencies of conventional educating. Since these customary methodologies don't urge understudies to address what they have realized or to connect with recently procured information, issue based learning is viewed as an imaginative measure to urge understudies to figure out how to learn by means of genuine issues.

Creative techniques for language teaching. Numerous mixed media advancements are accessible for developers to make these imaginative and intuitive sight and sound applications. The teacher applies multimedia and interactive techniques to enhance the substance of the material. It serves to educator to speak to in an increasingly important manner, utilizing diverse media components. These media components can be changed over into computerized structure, altered and tweaked for the last presentation. By fusing computerized media components into the task, the understudies can adapt better since they utilize numerous tactile modalities, which would make them increasingly persuaded to give careful consideration to the data exhibited and hold the data better. The new methods change the classroom experience. For instance, the room is set up with cameras for shooting whiteboards, so understudies can get the pictures as advanced documents. What's more, PCs minimized PCs that enable the instructor to compose notes straightforwardly on the screen with an exceptional pen, supplant the obsolete projector. Innovation enables educators and instructors to make notes on outlines and spreadsheets and send them straightforwardly to their understudies' PCs.

Standards of educating are the first arrangements that, taken together, characterize the prerequisites for the entire and its parts (objectives, targets, techniques, assets, authoritative structures, learning).

The guideline of learning is one of the essential classes of methods from a position, which characterizes the necessities for the instruction framework in general, and its individual segments. Core values in arranging and executing the instructive procedure: defining objectives and errands; the determination of the substance and strategies for educating [2; 30p]. The rule of visually or ostensive standard is acknowledged in immediate and visual methods of simonizing or clarifying implications, for example in the show and naming by the educator of articles, pictures and activities wherefrom the students surmise the implications

of words and articulations utilized. In foreign language teaching it is in some cases sensible to enable students to absorb, language governs instead of hold up until they reason these tenets through discourse movement. The educator's errand isn't to put this diligent work on the student's shoulders yet to encourage the procedure of principle learning and to rehearse it, all things considered, circumstances. We have considered the primary strategies and standards of foreign language teaching as models or ideal models of hypothesis, research and school practice. Some of them might be viewed as out of date from a logical perspective, some others appear to be progressively current, however in actuality every one of them have presented developments at a given minute, superimposing on the ones of every a mixed way. In any case, all strategies share no less than two things for all intents and purpose: 1) their conviction to be the best one, and 2) a lot of solutions that instructors need to pursue essentially. I don't propose then from the presumptions in this article showing ought to be moved toward following a specific technique as a lot of remedies, however despite what might be expected as a dynamic and intelligent procedure, which implies a lasting communication.

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